

Time Value Analysis of Driver Due to Traffic Jam During Bridge Construction: Case Study in Kalibone Bridge Construction Maros-Pangkep Axis, Indonesia

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Abstract

This paper discusses the time value analysis of a driver due to traffic jams during the Kalibone bridge construction. The bridge construction is one of west Sulawesi crossroad bridges in 2019 construction with 20m width and 58.4m span expected to serve trans Sulawesi west traffic. There are two approaches used to calculate this time value, which is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) based method and welfare maximization based method. The difference between the two methods is that the welfare level method includes leisure time value analysis, whereas the GDP method not included. The result indicated that the costs incurred by road users are time value of IDR 4.437 billion for Maros-Pangkep direction and IDR. 4.552 billion for Pangkep-Maros direction during the Kalibone Bridge construction project, which lasted 873 days with a difference in an increase during normal conditions of 873 days by 670% for Maros-Pangkep direction and 690% for the reverse direction.

Keywords: *Traffic jam, driver loss, people welfare, gross domestic product, bridge construction.*

1. Introduction

During the construction period, all roads in the project area will be affected by varying weights. Mobilization of heavy equipment (dump trucks, trailers), as well as material mobilization, will impact directly on road works [1]. Traffic movement will also disrupt road damage and narrowing of roads. The traffic disturbances for road users will be felt in reduced speed, increased travel time, increased stop-go—traffic jams marked by small headway between vehicles, and others [2]. In the long run, reducing spare parts life and increasing fuel and oil consumption [3].

It often happens in a project, with a particular construction time, not only thinking about the project's objectives but also analyzing the project's impact during implementation [4]. The impact is that people will be disturbed during project construction [5]–[8]. However, it not stated how severe the disturbance is and where the disturbance can minimize. These immeasurable forms or opportunity costs [9] tried to study by comparing the road conditions before and during the project construction. The parameter reviewed in this study is the travel time experienced by vehicles when crossing the Kalibone bridge construction. Therefore, this study aimed to calculate and compare travel time on Kalibone Bridge before and during construction and the costs incurred by road users due to the difference in travel time.

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2. Theoretical Review

2.1. Relationship of Traffic Parameters

There is a relationship between speed and density of traffic on a road section. The higher traffic density, then traffic speed will decrease. Likewise, there is a relationship between traffic volume and traffic speed. The volume will increase as speed increases toward where the volume reaches a maximum. After the point reached, the speed will decrease. The relationship between speed and traffic volume is parabolic [10], as in Equation 1.

$$Q = V \times D \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: Q = volume; V = vehicle speed; D = density

The relationship between travel time, vehicle speed and distance can be formulated as follows:

$$S = v \times T \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: T = Travel Time; v = vehicle speed; S = distance

The relationship is strongly influenced by speed, while speed strongly influences by road and traffic conditions. The more congested traffic and worse road conditions caused speed will decrease.

2.2. Average Daily Traffic Calculation

Average daily traffic (LHR) used to determine plan hour volume and calculated using the formula as follows [11].

$$Q_{\text{Max Hour.}} = \text{LHR} \times k \times \text{PHF} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where: $Q_{\text{Jam Maks}}$ = Maximum road volume; LHR = Average daily traffic; k = Conversion factor; PHF = Peak hour factor

The k factor is a conversion factor if only average daily traffic is knowing without traffic distribution known every hour. The magnitude of k factor can be estimated, the value influenced by city and road type. The k value, according to MKJI, is presented in Table 1 [11], whereas the k value, according to Matson et al. shown in Table 2 [12].

Table 1. Factors k According to the Indonesian Road Capacity Manual

City and Road Types	Percent Factor k
Cities with a population of > 1 million	
- Jalan- Roads on commercial areas and arterial roads	7-8%
- Road in residential areas	8-9%
Cities with a population of 1 million	
- Roads in commercial areas and arterial roads	8-10%
- Road in residential areas	9-12%

The peak hour factor (PHF) is the ratio of the volume during peak hours to the maximum current during a specific period in one hour. Traffic flow measurements usually use 15

minutes [13]. The peak hour factor used to determine fluctuations in traffic flow during specific observations.

$$PHF = Q_{PH} / (4 \times Q_{Maks\ 15\ menit}) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Table 2. Factors k according to Matson et al. [12]

Facility Type	k Factor
Rural	0.15 - 0.25
Sub urban	0.12 – 0.15
Urban:	
- Radial route	0.07 – 0.12
- Circumferental route	0.07 – 0.12

2.3. Time Value

Time value is composed of time value for the driver and time value for vehicle passengers. For passenger vehicles, the time value is still distinguished between passengers and business needs for each party, and the average number of passengers on each type of vehicle, and the time value for each type of vehicle can calculate. Table 3 showed the relationship between vehicle time value, vehicle types, and passenger number [14].

Table 3. Time Value of Vehicle Type

Vehicle Types	Average Passenger number per vehicle	Vehicle time type value (IDR/hr)		
		1988	1996	2009
Motorcycle	1,58	155,60	190,20	314,00
Passenger Car	2,27	513,00	627,00	1035,30
Pick-up	2,20	497,20	607,70	1003,40
Truck	3,00	1380,00	1686,60	2784,90
Mini Bus	5,95	410,00	501,80	828,60
Medium/Large Bus	12,27	846,60	1034,70	1708,50

Time value of vehicle type referring to Indonesian inflation in each region calculated using Table 3. There are two approaches used to calculate this time value, that is GDP based and welfare maximization based. The difference between the two is that the welfare level method includes the value of leisure time in the analysis, whereas the GDP method does not.

Data collected to prove that the construction consequences of the Kali Bone bridge are very influential on vehicle operating costs magnitude. Costs associated with the road surface layer of each element will change according to pavement quality changes of starting from the high-quality pavement, lower pavement, gravel or rock, and soil [15].

Vehicle operating costs in Indonesia are higher than average costs in other Asian countries. The difference in costs incurred is mainly due to differences in topography and road quality. The highest costs that must be borne by the primary road users by goods transportation companies are fuel oil, depreciation, and interest payments. The roughness

of the road surface has an impact on the magnitude of vehicle operating costs, therefore asphaltting on the road surface can reduce the vehicle operating cost.

3. Methodology of Study

The location of this study in Kalibone bridge construction Maros-Pangkep axis road, South Sulawesi, Indonesia as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Location of Study

This study is a survey method conducted in the Kalibone Bridge project development area. This location was determined based on the observation that this area was one of those affected by the widening of the Maros - Pangkep axis road. The first survey conduct on November 24, 2019, and the second survey on December 05, 2019.

The data used is primary data and secondary data, where primary data is comparative data before construction and field direct measuring of travel time data. While secondary data is LHR data before the project and obtained from the South Sulawesi Transportation Office, some of the additional data is data used to conduct the analysis.

4. Results Analysis

The traffic survey collected was taken on two different days, which is on office days and holidays, while the first survey conducted on November 24, 2019, and the second survey on December 5, 2019. Furthermore, the survey conduct in three times for one day, morning from 08.00 - 09.00, afternoon from 12.00 - 13.00, and evening from 17.00 - 18.00. Measurement of travel time is done by following several vehicles (passenger cars, small buses, medium buses, and large buses). The vehicle number data used obtained from the Department of Transportation, Communication, and Information of South Sulawesi Province in 2019. The results of a vehicle travel time survey represented in Table 4.

Tabel 4. Results Survey of Vehicle Travel Time

Time Survey	Route	Passenger Cars (Seconds)	Mini-Bus (Seconds)	Medium-Bus (Seconds)	Heavy-Bus (Seconds)
First Day Survey					
08.00 - 09.00	Maros - Pangkep	158	155	141	187
	Pangkep - Maros	134	128	151	177
12.00 - 13.00	Maros - Pangkep	108	111	132	168
	Pangkep - Maros	78	99	161	175
17.00 - 18.00	Maros - Pangkep	173	178	194	212
	Pangkep - Maros	177	184	207	231
Second Day Survey					
08.00 - 09.00	Maros - Pangkep	171	178	179	204
	Pangkep - Maros	167	173	182	192
12.00 - 13.00	Maros - Pangkep	127	120	114	110
	Pangkep - Maros	199	118	153	149
17.00 - 18.00	Maros -Pangkep	217	216	231	256
	Pangkep - Maros	202	198	215	229

Based on Table 4 showed that the maximum actual volume is in the time range of 17.00-18.00. The maximum traffic volume occurred was due to a large number of buses from outside the area going to Makassar, passing the Kalibone Bridge road.

The travel speed before bridge construction, according to MKJI road planning data, is 60 km/hour with bridge distance and observed point of 358.4 m. Based on this data, the travel time before the project is 21.50 seconds. Furthermore, travel time based on hourly survey results for Maros-Pangkep direction shown in Table 5 and Pangkep-Maros direction in Table 6.

Table 5. Travel Time Survey Results for Maros-Pangkep Direction

Survey Time: 08.00-09.00)				Survey Time: 12.00-13.00)				Survey Time: 17.00-18.00)			
Vehicle Types	Segment length (m)	Velocity (Km/jam)	Travel Time (Seconds)	Vehicle Types	Segment length (m)	Velocity (Km/jam)	Travel Time (Seconds)	Vehicle Types	Segment length (m)	Velocity (Km/jam)	Travel Time (Seconds)
Passenger Cars	358.4	8.17	158	Passenger Cars	358.4	11.95	108	Passenger Cars	358.4	7.46	173
Mini-Bus	358.4	8.32	155	Mini-Bus	358.4	11.62	111	Mini-Bus	358.4	7.25	178
Medium-Bus	358.4	7.55	141	Medium-Bus	358.4	9.77	132	Medium-Bus	358.4	6.65	194
Heavy-Bus	358.4	6.9	187	Heavy-Bus	358.4	7.68	168	Heavy-Bus	358.4	6.09	212

Tabel 6. Travel Time Survey Results for Pangkep-Maros Direction

Survey Time: 08.00-09.00)				Survey Time: 12.00-13.00)				Survey Time: 17.00-18.00)			
Vehicle Types	Segment length (m)	Velocity (Km/jam)	Travel Time (Seconds)	Vehicle Types	Segment length (m)	Velocity (Km/jam)	Travel Time (Seconds)	Vehicle Types	Segment length (m)	Velocity (Km/jam)	Travel Time (Seconds)
Passenger Cars	358.4	2.14	134	Passenger Cars	358.4	16.54	78	Passenger Cars	358.4	7.29	177
Mini-Bus	358.4	2.08	128	Mini-Bus	358.4	13.03	99	Mini-Bus	358.4	7.01	184
Medium-Bus	358.4	2.31	151	Medium-Bus	358.4	8.01	161	Medium-Bus	358.4	6.23	207
Heavy-Bus	358.4	2.57	177	Heavy-Bus	358.4	7.37	175	Heavy-Bus	358.4	5.59	231

Based on Table 5 and Table 6, the travel time and speed difference per direction determined when the bridge construction work carried out areas in Table 7.

Table 7. Speed and Time Travel Deviation Pre and During Construction

Speed of Plan (km/hr)	Average Speed During Construction (km/hr)	
	Maros - Pangkep	Pangkep - Maros
60	8.13	8.20
Speed Deviation	51.87	51.80
Pre-Construction Travel Time (seconds)	Average Travel Time on During Construction (seconds)	
	Maros - Pangkep	Pangkep - Maros
21.504	166.75	166.63
Travel Time Deviation	145.25	145.12

Based on Table 7 results, indicated that the Kalibone bridge construction causes the vehicle speed passing through the bridge to decrease and increasing travel time. It can understand that most bridge construction access to uses the Maros-Pangkep direction is a heavy equipment and material mobility. The tools and materials mobility using heavy vehicles requires a large area to support the smooth running of a project, which causes people to slow down their vehicle speed.

Moreover, time travel increased cause opportunity loss of road users to carry out other activities and measured as a time value. Meanwhile, the costs borne by Maros-Pangkep axis road users, there are two assumptions used that is trip and purpose status of the driver are the same. The costs incurred are only influenced by travel time and based on inflation data of 6.82% obtained from the South Sulawesi Data Center Agency, then known the time value of vehicle type as in Table 8, and average daily traffic data as shown in Table 9.

Table 8. Time Value of Vehicle Type

Vehicle Type	South Sulawesi Inflation Value	Time Value (IDR/hr)
Pessenger Cars	6.82%	1,105.91
Mini-Bus		885.11
Medium/Heavey-Bus		1,825.02

Table 9. Average daily traffic of South Sulawesi

Working Area	Vehicle Types			
	Passenger Cars	Mini-Bus	Medium-Bus	Heavy-Bus
UPDT LLAJ Makassar Area I	5507	7798	3503	2374
UPDT LLAJ Maros Area I	576	1366	884	628
UPDT LLAJ Pare Pare Area I	948	2288	1467	408

Furthermore, an analysis driver time value for Maros-Pangkep direction and Pangkep-Maros direction is shown in Table 10, while driver time value before construction as seen in Table 11.

Tabel 10. Driver Time Value of Maros-Pangkep and Pangkep-Maros Direction During Bridge Construction

Vehicle Types	LHR	Travel Time (km/hr)	Time Value (IDR/hr)	Driver Travel Time Value		
				Hour (IDR)	Day (IDR)	During Construction (IDR)
Maros-Pangkep Direction						
Passenger Cars	576	0.04	1105.91	25,480.17	611,523.99	533,860,446.41
Mini-Bus	1366	0.04	885.11	48,362.41	1,160,697.85	1,013,289,222.70
Medium-Bus	884	0.05	1825.02	80,665.88	1,935,981.22	1,690,111,601.57
Heavy-Bus	628	0.05	1825.02	57,305.63	1,375,335.07	1,200,667,517.86
Total Time Value of Driver During Construction						4,437,928,788.54
Pangkep-Maros Direction						
Passenger Cars	576	0.04	1105.91	25,863.55	620,725.16	541,893,068.87
Mini-Bus	1366	0.04	885.11	50,377.51	1,209,060.26	1,055,509,606.98
Medium-Bus	884	0.05	1825.02	79,844.29	1,916,262.89	1,672,897,501.92
Heavy-Bus	628	0.05	1825.02	61,179.06	1,468,297.54	1,281,823,748.23
Total Time Value of Driver During Construction						4,552,123,926.00

Tabel 11. Driver Time Value Before Construction

Vehicle Types	LHR	Travel Time (km/hr)	Time Value (IDR/hr)	Driver Travel Time Value in Normal Condition		
				Hour (IDR)	Day (IDR)	For 873 days (IDR)
Passenger Cars	576	0.006	1,105.91	3,805.04	91,320.92	79,723,160.00
Mini-Bus	1366	0.006	885.11	7,222.12	173,330.88	151,317,857.26
Medium-Bus	884	0.006	1,825.02	9,636.88	231,285.22	201,911,999.33
Heavy-Bus	628	0.006	1,825.02	6,846.11	164,306.70	143,439,746.13
Total Time Value of Driver for 873 days						576,392,762.72

Therefore, based on the driver time value before and during bridge construction, it is known the percentage increase of driver time value for the two opposite directions during construction, as shown in Table 12. Based on the table, the percentage increase average driver's time value for passenger cars of 575%, mini-buses of 584%, medium-buses of 733%, and heavy-buses of 765.5% while the average total increase during construction was 680%.

Table 12. Percentage Increase in Rider Time Value During Bridge Construction

Vehicle Types	Driver Travel Time Value			
	Normal Condition (IDR)	During Bridge Construction (IDR)	Cost Increases (IDR)	%

Maros-Pangkep Direction				
Passenger Cars	79,723,160.00	533,860,446.41	454,137,286.42	570%
Mini-Bus	151,317,857.26	1,013,289,222.70	861,971,365.44	570%
Medium-Bus	201,911,999.33	1,690,111,601.57	1,488,199,602.23	737%
Heavy-Bus	143,439,746.13	1,200,667,517.86	1,057,227,771.72	737%
Increase During Construction	576,392,762.72	4,437,928,788.54	3,861,536,025.82	670%
Pangkep-Maros Direction				
Passenger Cars	79.723.160,00	541.893.068,87	462.169.908,87	580%
Mini-Bus	151.317.857,26	1.055.509.606,98	904.191.749,72	598%
Medium-Bus	201.911.999,33	1.672.897.501,92	1.470.985.502,59	729%
Heavy-Bus	143.439.746,13	1.281.823.748,23	1.138.384.002,10	794%
Increase During Construction	576.392.762,72	4.552.123.926,00	3.975.731.163,28	690%

5. Conclusion

Construction projects, especially roads and bridges, certainly have positive and negative impacts on the public interest, likewise the construction of the Kalibone bridge on the Maros-Pangkep South Sulawesi axis road. The study concludes that during construction, there was an increase in the average driver time value for passenger cars of 575%, mini-buses of 584%, medium-buses of 733%, and heavy-buses of 765.5% while the average total increase during construction was 680%. Therefore, the effort that needs before construction is a collaboration between the project party and road users or the community to provide socialization by placing banners or advertisements explaining disturbances existence to road users due to the project. Besides, the access road to the construction site must clear from side obstacles in the form of material piles and a queue of project vehicles around the site on certain days.

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